

PROMOTING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENT YOUTH

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Abstract. *Changes in the educational process taking place in the whole duyo most student young people's educational process radically changes in connection with this change in their lifestyle and, as a result, they are experiencing an increase in the number of certain diseases associated with these very conditions as a result of which the transition of various diseases among students, the origin of disability cases or the increasing incidence and mortality among the population is increasingly reflected in the fact that changing the lifestyles of our student youth can further increase the chances of our young people reading and learning in a healthy state by introducing teaching them the principles of a healthy lifestyle. It is known that in our society, human health, physical perfection, the possession of a healthy lifestyle culture is an extremely important social value. Youth health is one of the most basic indicators of Population Health, it is a kind of barometer - indicator that shows the social economic development of the country, the state of sanitary - demography of the population, the quality of medical care, the effectiveness of sanitary - epidemiological, preventive and therapeutic work.*

Improving the health of students, among them the widespread promotion of a healthy lifestyle measures aimed at reducing the number of currently common diseases that can occur in them, are considered one of the main factors that lead to an increase in average life expectancy. Therefore, the study of youth health and the development of a scientifically based measure to improve it from the medical and social nature is considered one of the first social issues of the current era.

The purpose of the study: to study a healthy lifestyle among student youth and to assess the specifics of studying the factors affecting the lifestyle, the risk of habits harmful to their health.

Keywords: *healthy lifestyle, student youth, agenda.*

According to the World Health Organization (who) (who Information Bulletin April 2017), 40 million people die of non-infectious diseases (NICS) each year, accounting for 70% of the world's total deaths. Each year, 17 million people under the age of 70 die of Nick. Low-and middle-income countries account for 87% of these 'early' deaths. The most kata share in the composition of Nick death corresponds to cardiovascular diseases, which indicates that 17.7 million people lose their lives for this reason every year.

Material and methods of research. The results of comparing the incidence in groups that differ in the influence of the risk factor can be presented in the form of several indicators. Medical-sociological research involves the problems of students of higher educational institutions associated with the issues of a healthy lifestyle, allowing the formation of the main motivational idea.

Among the study participants, 68% are women and 32% are men. The age of the respondents is 18-23 years. Equal groups were provided to distribute respondents according to the age distribution of survey participants, the course of training. Students were initially asked to assess the quality of their lifestyle, with the majority of those surveyed rating their quality as good (56.0%) and excellent (21.0%). Every fifth person is satisfied with the parameter, and only a few chose the categories “bad” and “very bad”.

Results. A preliminary survey was conducted of 400 students of working age who had Arterial hypertension and had organizational risks. As part of the next survey, representatives of the areas of Medicine (Med) and pedagogy (Ped) were studied. The survey is associated with the concept of a “healthy lifestyle” of students of higher educational institutions. With the data obtained accordingly, students associate a healthy lifestyle. First of all, concepts such as the organization of proper nutrition, good health status and physical activity were taken as one of the foundations of this survey.

Figure 1. Linking respondents ' understanding of a “healthy lifestyle” (% , N=568)

The next survey is important for understanding student leadership motivation. In this case, the main goal is to determine the reasons for the refusal of a healthy lifestyle of students from Sports. It is natural that there are reasons for not wanting to exercise, showed that students ' free time is not due to the high influence of these factors. For example: while there is employment (56.0%), family conditions (18.7%), treatment with health (10.8%), more than 16% of respondents believe that daily actions are sufficient to maintain good physical condition. In addition, laziness, as well as lack of motivation, have been studied to be the main causes of sports withdrawal for every tenth respondent.

Figure 2. The main factors that prevent students of higher educational institutions from regularly engaging in sports

It is normal for a student of a higher educational institution to be occupied by physical and mental labor during the day of youth. Most students do not follow the agenda working hours, do not have an understanding of the rest routine.

Figure 3. The distribution of student respondents was based on the answers to the question “Do you follow the agenda?”

Conclusion. The results obtained showed that medic-students understand a healthy lifestyle and its importance in human health, but do not follow it.

In physical training and sports clubs, most students expressed a desire to participate, but insisted that there were time and family problems.

Students of the higher educational institution are instrumental in the formation of healthy lifestyle skills due to the correct distribution of their free time, compliance with the agenda, rest and working order. Therefore, the development of youth health with a scientifically based measure to improve health from the medical and social nature is considered one of the first social tasks of the current era.

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